

What is real estate development?

[Real estate developer](#) Abraham Leser points out that a somewhat unknown concept, "real estate development" can be compared to real estate development. Indeed, when a need is identified, a company specializing in real estate development has the task of transforming it into a project.

When real estate development is part of the management of a project, it most often corresponds to land development. In other words, the objective will be to do everything possible to find a building plot and to acquire it at the best price with a view to its subsequent resale.

The different stages of real estate development

[Abraham Leser](#) indicates that real estate development can be broken down into 3 main stages:

Prospecting. It is undoubtedly the most time-consuming step, as finding a building plot can be complex even for real estate professionals. Indeed, the plots of land available are not as numerous as it seems. So, when there are geographic but also budgetary constraints, it sometimes comes down to looking for a needle in a haystack.

Therefore, in order for the prospecting to be successful, the land developer must be able to count on a large business network and be in contact with various partners likely to help him, whether they are individuals or agents. real estate (learn more about training to become a real estate agent in Switzerland), notaries, etc ... He must also be able to carry out the assembly of the project in order to be able to obtain the building permit

The presentation of the real estate project. [The experienced real estate executive](#), Abraham Leser In setting up any real estate program, it is essential that all future customer needs be taken into account. Indeed, for the project to attract future customers, it must meet their expectations in terms of both price and services provided.

However, Abraham Leser indicates that, a technical, legal and financial pre-study must confirm that it is indeed possible to carry out the desired project in the chosen field. If everything seems to corroborate the selection of the plot to build, it is time to take steps to acquire it

The implementation of the real estate project. Because the project must comply with all the regulations in force, it must be ensured that it is in line with the urban plans with the architect before validating it.

Once the validation has been confirmed, Abraham Leser, [the founder of the Leser Group](#), that it will be time to take the steps to obtain the various administrative authorizations. Soon, the site will be able to begin and it will therefore be time to constitute the teams who will carry the project on site.